

Genomic underpinnings of sex differences in health and disease

ACADEMY OF FINLAND DMP

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1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF DATA

1.1 What kinds of data are collected or reused?

The project builds on the reuse of data that has been collected previously (e.g. FINRISK, GTEx, UKBB) or is being produced as part of other projects (e.g. Human Cell Atlas, pending approvals from the data owners / access committees). The data types include:

- RNA sequencing data, both bulk and single cell
- genotype data from sequencing(WGS & WES) and array genotyping
- phenotype data, e.g., laboratory measurements
- registry data, e.g. hospital discharge and drug purchase registries
- Data generated in the project are
 - analysis results and
 - data summaries of the above-mentioned input data.

1.2 What file formats will the data be in?

Sequencing data: fastq and bam (raw); VCF (called/processed genotypes).

Genotype array data: intensity data (raw); VCF, PLINK format (bim/bam/fam files) and/or Oxford format (.gen files) (called/processed genotypes)

Phenotype data: .txt or .xls files, SQL database

Data summaries and results: .txt files or similar

The genotype array and sequencing data formats are aligned with the field standards, and allow processing with several types of tools (e.g. for sequence alignment).

2. DOCUMENTATION AND QUALITY

2.1 How will the data be documented?

As the PI is not the primary owner of the input data sets being utilized, the key responsibility for the documentation of the collection and generation of these data is not with the PI but in the hands of the data owners. For example, the GTEx and UKBB data collection and processing are described on the resource websites (<https://gtexportal.org/home/> and <http://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk>) and the consortium publications (e.g. The GTEx Consortium. Science. 8 May 2015: Vol 348 no. 6235 pp 648-660.).

The analysis data will be in .txt format or other standard format accessible to other users, the processing and analysis procedures, with appropriate README files for guidance, will be documented in GitHub (<https://github.com>). The results are linked to input data with ID codes, accession number(s), or other codes described in the pipeline documentation or data deposition archive metadata.

The PI has committed to high community standards in reporting data processing protocols (e.g. through experience in the ExAC project). Pipelines for data processing and analysis, which the PI and her group are responsible for (e.g. GTEx, UKBB, single-cell), will be documented and made public in GitHub.

2.2 How will the consistency and quality of data be controlled and documented?

The expert data management team at the Human Genomics research unit at FIMM has implemented data quality control pipelines for the processing of genotype data and the related phenotype data. These are available for all internal users through a wiki hosted by the University of Helsinki and will later be described in publications utilizing the data.

3. STORAGE AND BACKUP

3.1 How will the data be stored and backed up?

The Finnish genotype data is currently stored on the (local) FIMM servers, which are automatically backed up and managed by the FIMM IT team. The other data utilized in the project will be transferred, upon downloading from dbGaP or other archives, to the FIMM server, analyzed in the FIMM computing cluster environment, and all analysis results and other data generated in the reuse of the input data are stored on the same FIMM server. If an alternative solution to data storage is required, the PI will use a virtual sever hosted and backed up by the Finnish IT center CSC.

3.2 How will you control access to keep the data secure?

The individual level registry data is of high sensitivity and requires special security measures. If access to registry data on this level is granted to the PI, the data will be stored and queried at a dedicated server on CSC (ePouta: <https://research.csc.fi/epouta>) that complies with VAHTI 3 requirements.

4. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

4.1 How will ethical issues be managed?

Regarding existing data, the original data collection and application have been approved by appropriate ethical committees. In case of new uses of the data, the researcher will confirm (together with the data access committee in question) that the planned analysis is compliant with the original ethical approval.

4.2 How will ownership, copyright and Intellectual Property Right (IPR) issues be managed?

The ownership of the analysis data and results will be confirmed with collaboration contracts signed by every research partner. The partners agree to transfer the ownership to the PI (unless transfer of the rights to another research partner is more justified). Similarly partners will sign a contract agreeing that data arising from the research project will be made openly available where possible. Regarding IPR, the project will follow University of Helsinki invention guidelines.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 How, when, where and to whom will the data be made available?

As the ownership of the data sets utilized, is not with the PI, the PI has no right to share or make the raw data publicly available. Where possible, summary statistics and other results that do not breach the anonymity requirement will be made available in publications and/or data repositories (European Nucleotide Archive, <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>). The pipelines for data processing and analysis which the PI and her group are responsible for (e.g. GTEx, UKBB, single-cell) will be made public in GitHub.

5.2 How and where will the data with long-term value be made available?

Currently, the University of Helsinki does not provide a suitable long-term storage for the data generated in the project. The PI will be in active contact with the data management team in the university to be updated for possible solutions emerging. Regarding data that is not available in public databases, outside researchers will be able to contact the PI to gain access to such files.

5.3 Have you estimated costs in time and effort to prepare the data for preservation and sharing?

Open science is already an integral part of the PIs research work. In total, approximately 40 hours per year is put into data sharing or deposition and the included documentation procedures.